

Experimental Characterization of Propeller Induced Flow (PIF) Around a Multi-Rotor Drone

Master thesis

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Preface

This master's thesis has been an enlightening journey in exploring the potential use of drone systems in atmospheric research to enhance our understanding of wake propagation in and around wind farms. The rapidly growing demand for sustainable energy sources has led to increased interest in wind energy, and understanding the wake dynamics in wind farms is crucial to optimize their efficiency and performance. Applying drone systems in this field opens new data collection and analysis possibilities, ultimately contributing to advancing wind energy technology.

Firstly I want to express my deepest gratitude to my advisors, Joachim Reuder, Stephan Thomas Kral, and Mauro Ghirardelli, for their invaluable guidance, support, and expertise throughout this thesis. Their advice and input have continuously provided a guiding hand. I also want to especially thank Joachim for always taking the time to listen and answer when I have had questions.

I also want to thank the Atmospheric Boundary Layer Research Group for their collaboration and for providing much-valued feedback and expertise every Thursday at one.

Lastly, I want to thank my fellow students and classmates. The experienced and friendships we have made over the last years through pandemics, trips, long days, and longer nights are something I am genuinely grateful for, and I am already looking forward to the experiences we will have in the future.

As we continue to explore the potential of wind energy and other renewable energy sources, I hope this thesis's findings can contribute to the ongoing effort to create a sustainable future for all.

Alexander Arvid Flem, June 1st, 2023.

Abstract

Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) used in atmospheric research present a promising approach for advancing our understanding of wake propagation in and around wind farms, leading to more optimized layouts and increasing efficiency and performance. This master's thesis focuses on generating and analyzing a comprehensive dataset of the propeller-induced flow (PIF) produced by the UAV used in the SAMURAI (Sonic Anemometer on a MUlti-Rotor drone for Atmospheric turbulence Investigations) project within a calm environment.

To achieve this, an experiment was designed and conducted that mapped the PIF along numerous measurement planes perpendicular and tangential to the mean velocity of the downwash, using an array of five sonic anemometers. The experiment design involved mounting the drone at a 90-degree angle to its flying orientation. By doing so, the downwash was moving and developing horizontally to avoid ground effects. The five sonic anemometers were mounted to a mast, vertically separated by 50 cm. The mounting of the mast on an adjustable table allowed for subsequent height adjustments, increasing the vertical resolution to 10 cm. The resulting dataset maps the PIF from two rotor diameters, $D = 71 \text{ cm}$, beneath the rotor plane, to ten D , and from the center line of the downwash to three D off the center line. This measurement strategy resulted in a detailed three-dimensional picture of the downwash of the drone in high spatial resolution.

The experimental results show that PIF quickly decreases when moving away from the centerline of the wake in a direction parallel to the rotor plane. After one D , the experimental data show PIF less than four m/s within the first five D beneath the drone, and no conclusive disturbance measured at two D . PIF greater than four m/s was still observed along the center of the downwash for both throttle settings tested (35% and 45%), ten D under the rotor plane. Within the first four D under the rotor plane, convergence towards the center of the downwash was measured before changing to diverging, causing the downwash to expand. The turbulent velocity fluctuations within the downwash were also measured and were shown to be greatest towards the edges, where the shear between the PIF and stagnant air is the greatest.

The objective of the thesis was to find areas of minimal PIF and, therefore, more suitable for sensor placement. The mentioned results indicate that the region one to

two D out from the center of the downwash and within three D beneath the rotor plane seems to be best suited for sensor placement. The thesis also set out to provide validation data for a set of CFD simulations performed by Ghirardelli et al. (2023). The data gathered indicate that the simulations fall within an acceptable margin of experimental conditions. How PIF structure relates to the applied throttle setting was also an area of interest, but lack of data hindered a decisive conclusion.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Global Warming and the Problem of the Current Energy Landscape .	1
1.2	The Role of Wind Energy in the Energy Transition	3
1.3	The Challenge Facing Wind Energy	4
1.4	The Emergence of UAARS	5
1.5	Objectives	6
2	Background Information	8
2.1	Wind and Turbulence	8
2.1.1	Turbulence and Turbulent Kinetic Energy	9
2.1.2	Vertical Distribution of Wind Energy	10
2.2	Extraction of Wind Energy	11
2.3	Modeling and Predicting Wake Characteristics and Behaviour	14
2.4	Turbine-Defined Flow Regions	15
2.4.1	The Near-Wake	15
2.4.2	The Far-Wake	17
2.5	Park-Defined Flow Regions	18
2.5.1	Wind Farm Induction Zone	19
2.5.2	Entrance and Flow Development Region	19
2.5.3	The Fully Developed Wind Turbine Array Boundary Layer	20
2.5.4	The Exit and Wind Farm Wake Region	20

2.6	The Need For New Datasets	20
2.7	Traditional Methods for Obtaining Wind Measurements	22
2.8	UAARS	23
2.8.1	Some Approaches Taken to UAARS	23
2.8.2	Limitations of UAARS	24
2.9	SAMURAI	25
2.9.1	The Importance of Understanding UAV-Induced Disturbances	25
2.9.2	CFD Simulations	26
3	Data Acquisition	30
3.1	Experiment Design	30
3.2	Experiment Setup	33
3.3	PIF Mapping Procedure	38
4	Data Analysis	41
4.1	Cleaning and Correction of Spatial Points in DS2	41
4.2	Merging DS1 and DS2	43
4.3	Cleaning and Correction of Velocity Vectors in R	43
4.4	Calculation of UAV Induced Disturbance	44
5	Results	45
5.1	Quantification of Background Flow and Movement-Induced Velocities	45
5.2	Three Dimensional Characterisation of PIF	47
5.2.1	PIF Across XZ-Planes	48

Contents	vi
5.2.2 PIF Along YZ-Planes	51
5.2.3 Wake Expansion	55
5.2.4 PIF Variability	58
6 Conclusion	61
6.1 Objective 1: Mapping and Characterization of PIF Generated By SAMURAI UAV	61
6.2 Objective 2: CFD Validation	62
6.3 Objective 3: Correlation Between Throttle Settings and PIF	63
7 Outlook	65
Appendices	72
Appendix A The U_x Component of the PIF	72
A.1 35% Throttle Setting	72
A.2 45% Throttle Setting	75
Appendix B The U_y Component of the PIF	77
B.1 35% Throttle Setting	77
B.2 45% Throttle Setting	79
Appendix C The U_z Component of the PIF	81
C.1 35% Throttle Setting	81
C.2 45% Throttle Setting	83
Appendix D Distribution of TKE in the PIF	85

D.1 35% Throttle Setting	85
D.2 45% Throttle Setting	87

Abbreviations

- **ABL** - Atmospheric Boundary Layer
- **CFD** - Computational Fluid Dynamics
- **CL** - Center Line
- **GCS** - Ground Control Station
- **HAWT** - Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
- **IBL** - Internal Boundary Layer
- **IEA** - International Energy Agency
- **IMU** - Inertial Measurement Unit
- **JARUS** - Joint Authorities for Rulemaking on Unmanned Systems
- **LCOE** - Levelized Cost of Energy
- **LES** - Large Eddy Simulation
- **LIDAR** - Light Detection and Ranging
- **MAD** - Median Absolute Deviation
- **MKE** - Mean Kinetic Energy
- **mUAS** - Micro Uncrewed Aerial System
- **NaN** - Not a Number
- **NDC** - Nationally Determined Contributions
- **NZE 2050** - Net Zero Emissions 2050
- **PIF** - Propeller Induced Flow
- **RANS** - Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations
- **SAMURAI** - Sonic Anemometer on a Multi-Rotor drone for Atmospheric turbulence Investigations
- **SDG** - Sustainable Development Goals

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- **SODAR** - Sonic Detection and Ranging
 - **T35, T45** - 35% throttle setting, 45% throttle setting
 - **TKE** - Turbulent Kinetic Energy
 - **UAARS** - Uncrewed Aerial Atmospheric Research System
 - **UAS** - Uncrewed Aerial Systems
 - **UAV** - Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle
 - **UN** - United Nations
 - **UNFCCC** - United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
 - **VAWT** - Vertical Axis Wind Turbine
 - **WTABL** - Wind Turbine Array Boundary Layer

1 Introduction

The threat of global warming continues to grow, underlining the unsustainable nature of our current energy system, which primarily relies on fossil fuels. The broad impacts of our energy decisions bring grave implications for our biosphere's sustainability. Wind energy has become essential to the global energy shift, providing a sustainable, renewable alternative to fossil fuels. Despite its undeniable potential, the further advancement of wind energy also faces obstacles. Many of these hurdles stem from the need for a detailed understanding of the airflow around wind turbines and wind farms (Veers et al., 2019; Meneveau, 2019), and require a deeper understanding of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer, ABL, in particular on the complex interactions between wind shear, turbulence, and atmospheric stability. Traditionally, ABL measurements have been performed using sonic anemometers on masts or towers (Mauder et al., 2021). Although these systems deliver high-resolution atmospheric turbulence measurements, they suffer from limited mobility and flexibility. In particular, offshore masts are expensive and logistically demanding. Uncrewed Aerial Atmospheric Research Systems (UAARS) have begun to take center stage in addressing the need for better data, leveraging cutting-edge drone technology to enhance our understanding of turbulence and fill the recognized knowledge gaps. This thesis seeks to investigate the role and challenges of wind energy in the energy transition, the emergence and potential of UAARS, and provide an overview of the SAMURAI (Sonic Anemometer on a Multi-Rotor drone for Atmospheric turbulence Investigations) project, emphasizing how it stands out from other UAARS.

1.1 Global Warming and the Problem of the Current Energy Landscape

Over the last decades, the reality of anthropogenic climate change and its severity has become increasingly prevalent. The rising temperatures caused by an increased concentration of greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere are causing components of the climate system to shift, posing a significant threat to life on our planet with far-reaching consequences affecting ecosystems, human health, and economies (Bellard et al., 2012; Hallegatte et al., 2010). These changes include unsettling oceanic and atmospheric circulation patterns leading to shifting precipitation patterns and increased

frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, such as heatwaves, droughts, and storms (*Consequences of climate change* 2023). This has made it clear that humanity's current attitude towards resource management is unsustainable and must change if future generations are to experience the same living conditions as those enjoyed by current generations.

To address these changes and create a unified effort to tackle climate change several international commitments have been made, with the two most prominent being United Nations' (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) (UN, 2023), and the Paris Climate Accords hosted by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (UNFCCC, 2015). Established in 2015, the SDGs consist of 17 interconnected goals that provide a blueprint for achieving a more sustainable future by 2030 (UN, 2023). These goals encompass a wide range of social, economic, and environmental issues, such as poverty, inequality, education, health, and environmental sustainability. SDG 13, Climate Action, directly addresses the need to combat climate change and its impacts. While 7, Affordable and Clean Energy, addresses how development of the energy sector is essential. The Paris Climate Accords, adopted in December 2015, is a legally binding international treaty under the UNFCCC, making the 196 signing parties commit to climate action plans on a national level, known as nationally determined contributions (NDCs). Each successive NDC is meant to reflect an increasingly higher degree of ambition compared to the previous version. The accord's primary goal is to limit global warming to well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels, ideally to 1.5 °C, by reducing greenhouse gas emissions (UNFCCC, 2015). Together these initiatives have put pressure on governments to act, with many countries setting their focus on renewable energy. In pursuit of the 1.5-degree target established by the Paris Agreement, the necessity of transitioning towards a more sustainable energy mix is evident. Such a transition would involve the widespread adoption of cleaner, renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. Paving the way for a greener and more resilient energy future, as the current energy landscape is marked by a heavy reliance on fossil fuels. Electricity and heat production by fossil fuels currently account for 42.8% of global greenhouse gas emissions, where coal is the biggest contributor (IEA, 2022a).

The reliance on fossil fuels has also presented significant challenges in terms of energy security and market vulnerability. This is in large part due to the uneven distribution of resources across the globe resulting in the industry being predominantly

controlled by few major stakeholders with substantial fossil fuel reserves (Mason, 2012). This vulnerability became apparent during the SARS-CoV-19 pandemic of 2020-2022 and was further intensified by the subsequent conflict between Ukraine and Russia. The latter event led to strict import tariffs being put on Russian natural gas, of which they are Europe's largest source. This drove up energy prices considerably compared to pre-war and pre-pandemic levels, increasing the cost of living in Europe and highlighting the importance of SDG 7. This situation has underscored the urgency of diversifying energy portfolios and investing in alternative, renewable energy sources to mitigate the risks associated with the highly concentrated and imbalanced fossil fuel market.

1.2 The Role of Wind Energy in the Energy Transition

Wind energy has emerged as a cornerstone in the renewable energy mix contributing to 23% of the global renewable energy production (IEA, 2022b), and playing a pivotal role in shaping the sustainable energy landscape of tomorrow. According to data from the International Energy Agency (IEA), global installed capacity has grown from 180 GW in 2010 to 825 GW in 2021, and this trend is expected to continue in the coming years (IEA, 2022c). If the goals defined by IEA's Net Zero Emissions by 2050 roadmap, NZE 2050, is to be reached (IEA, 2021), the estimated annual addition of installed capacity needed to be on track in 2030 is close to 250 GW (IEA, 2022c), more than double that of 2020's record growth (Shown in Fig 1).

To achieve the full potential of wind energy and maintain the growth necessary to meet the targets set by the Paris Agreement, it is vital to optimize the utilization of this renewable resource. As a result, wind turbines have grown in size to access the more stationary, less turbulent winds above the surface layer, thereby improving energy capture. However, the increase in size also leads to more pronounced effects on wind propagation and interactions with local atmospheric conditions, which can significantly impact both the power output of wind farms and neighboring turbines, as well as the lifespan of individual turbines. These interactions have revealed a knowledge gap in our understanding of how turbines and farms influence their surroundings (Veers et al., 2019; Meneveau, 2019). In the emerging offshore sector, the absence of comprehensive data to understand these complex interactions in new environments is even more pronounced, potentially hindering the sector's development (Veers et al.,

Figure 1: Wind power generation, and needed wind power generation in 2030 to be on track for the Net Zero Scenario. Graphic obtained from *Wind Electricity IEA (2022c)*

2019).

1.3 The Challenge Facing Wind Energy

The limited understanding of turbine-flow interactions has emerged as one of the primary constraints on the further development of wind energy (Veers et al., 2019). This knowledge gap can largely be attributed to limitations associated with traditional measuring techniques, such as mast-mounted anemometers, Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR), and sonic detection and ranging (SODAR). The main limitation of these systems lies in their restricted resolution and spatial flexibility. Although they have offered valuable insights into turbine- and park-flow interactions so far, their shortcomings hinder their effectiveness as the wind industry evolves. Addressing this challenge necessitates the development of a measuring method capable of mapping airstreams with high spatio-temporal resolution over extensive areas, often in complex terrain.

1.4 The Emergence of UAARS

In recent years, Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles, UAVs, have emerged as promising solutions to address the limitations of traditional measurement techniques in ABL research (Fuertes et al., 2019; Neumann et al., 2015; Jacob et al., 2018; Elston et al., 2015). This paper uses UAV and drone as umbrella terms to reference an uncrewed airborne platform weighing under 25 kg. UAS, Uncrewed Aerial System, refers to a drone carrying a sensor suit. While UAARS, Uncrewed Aerial Atmospheric Research System, will refer specifically to UAS platforms designed and used for atmospheric research. It is worth mentioning that current UAS technology is not fully autonomous and still requires human supervision for task execution (Bange et al., 2021). The advantages offered by UAARS are:

High spatial and temporal resolution: Drones equipped with advanced sensors, such as sonic anemometers or pressure probes, can provide data with high spatio-temporal resolution.

Flexibility and maneuverability: Drones have the ability to gather data in a wide range of environments from different perspectives and altitudes, making them a versatile tool for mapping the ABL. For instance, in wind energy, UAVs can be dispatched in diverse wind farm terrains, maneuvering around wind turbines to collect valuable data. Their use is particularly advantageous in areas with complex terrains, such as the offshore setting, as their operation is not dependent on permanent infrastructure and can be operated from boats or transformer stations.

Cost-effectiveness and scalability: Drone-based measurement systems can be more cost-effective than traditional methods, particularly in remote or offshore locations where deploying and maintaining measurement equipment is challenging. Additionally, multiple drones can be deployed simultaneously to gather data across a larger area, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the wind farm environment.

These systems provide a flexible and cost-effective option for conducting measurements with high precision and accuracy, reducing research gaps by allowing researchers to collect data in previously inaccessible or difficult-to-reach potentially hazardous areas. This can lead to a better understanding of the flow phenomenon generated by energy extraction, as well as atmospheric processes, and can provide

valuable information for forecasting and the prediction of weather.

1.5 Objectives

One UAARS currently in development is the 'Sonic Anemometer on a MUlti-Rotor drone for Atmospheric turbulence Investigations' (SAMURAI) project, which aims to mount a research-grade sonic anemometer to a heavy lifting drone. To ensure that the SAMURAI system serves as a viable platform for atmospheric research, it is essential to position the anemometer in an area with minimal flow distortion induced by the drone's propellers. Achieving this necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the flow conditions around the UAV while hovering. Consequently, the need for this understanding has led to the formulation of three primary objectives that this thesis aims to achieve:

1. **Objective 1:** Generate a comprehensive dataset of the Propeller Induced Flow, PIF, produced by the SAMURAI UAV in a calm environment, and quantify the circulation pattern in the vicinity of the UAV while hovering. This will enhance the research team's understanding of the UAS's impact on the surrounding environment during flight and its potential to disrupt the results and measurements when used as the platform for a UAARS.
2. **Objective 2:** Provide realistic boundary conditions and input parameters, as well as a validation data set, for a series of CFD simulations that have been performed to simulate the influence of the UAV on the surrounding air while hovering.
3. **Objective 3:** Investigate how varying the throttle setting for a hovering system alters the characteristics and intensity of the induced circulations around the drone.

These objectives collectively aim to enhance the research groups understanding of the aerodynamic properties and behavior of the UAV system under different conditions. By examining how the UAV interacts with its environment and how different throttle settings affect the induced flow, the team can better identify regions to avoid when determining the optimal location of the sonic anemometer. All these efforts

contribute to validating the SAMURAI platform as a reliable solution for flexible airborne turbulence measurements.

2 Background Information

The following section provides the background information needed for understanding the challenge facing wind energy addressed in this thesis. In addition, it highlights how UAARS, such as SAMURAI, could play a vital role in overcoming these challenges.

2.1 Wind and Turbulence

Wind is generated due to the sun's differential heating of the Earth's surface, leading to temperature differences and, in turn, variations in atmospheric pressure. The pressure gradients that occur due to these variations exert a force on the surrounding air mass, pointing from the region of high pressure toward the region of low pressure. As the air reacts to the force, it starts to move, generating wind. However, due to the rotation of the Earth, this movement is affected by the Coriolis effect, which deflects the wind to the right in the Northern Hemisphere and to the left in the Southern Hemisphere, altering the wind's original path from simply high pressure to low pressure. Neglecting frictional forces, the pressure gradient force and the Coriolis effect balance each other, leading to what is known as geostrophic balance. This balance results in the wind flowing along the isobars, lines of constant atmospheric pressure, rather than directly from high to low pressure. This circulation pattern is clockwise around high-pressure areas and counterclockwise around low-pressure areas in the Northern Hemisphere, with the patterns reversed in the Southern Hemisphere.

This movement of air, as with any moving matter, contains kinetic energy. The amount of kinetic energy, E_k , contained in the wind is defined by the amount of fluid moved, represented by its mass, m , and the velocity at which it travels, U .

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}mU^2 = \frac{1}{2}\rho AU^3 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } m = \rho AU. \quad (2)$$

The air's velocity can be divided into two groups. The mean wind, denoted by \bar{U} , which represents the average velocity of the fluid, and fluctuations in velocity around

the mean, denoted by \bar{u} , known as turbulence. The total velocity, U , is the sum of these two components:

$$U = \bar{U} + u'. \quad (3)$$

2.1.1 Turbulence and Turbulent Kinetic Energy

Turbulence can be defined as chaotic three-dimensional eddies over a wide range of spatio-temporal scales (Stull, 1988). In the field of wind energy, turbulence is significant as it represents kinetic energy that cannot be extracted to the same extent as that of the mean flow. This differentiation also implies that the kinetic energy within the wind can be separated into mean kinetic energy, MKE , and turbulent kinetic energy, TKE .

$$E_k = MKE + TKE \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{MKE}{m} = \frac{1}{2}(\bar{U}^2 + \bar{V}^2 + \bar{W}^2) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{TKE}{m} = \frac{1}{2}(\overline{u'^2} + \overline{v'^2} + \overline{w'^2}), \quad (6)$$

where U, V , and W are the velocity components along the x, y , and z axis, respectively.

The largest eddies in the atmosphere are generated by the bulk shear that forms between the free atmosphere, where the wind is governed by geostrophic balance, and the Earth's surface, where frictional effects play a significant role. This differential movement creates shear, facilitating large-scale turbulence. These large eddy motions then generate wind shear with their surroundings, leading to the shedding of kinetic energy into smaller eddies. This transfer of TKE from large-scale to smaller-scale eddies is known as the energy cascade, one of the key characteristics of turbulence (Stull, 1988). The energy transport into smaller scales continues down to the molecular level, where viscous and internal forces dissipate the kinetic energy into thermal

energy, thus this effect acts as a sink of kinetic energy (Manwell et al., 2010). The scale in the cascade at which internal forces overcome the kinetic forces are known as The Kolmogorov scale and is determined by the kinematic viscosity, ν , of the fluid, and the dissipation rate of the turbulent kinetic energy, ε (Stull, 1988):

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\nu^3}{\varepsilon}\right)^{1/4}. \quad (7)$$

The distribution of energy across the scales of turbulence can be represented through a turbulence spectrum. The larger more energetic eddies in the energy-containing range of the turbulence spectrum are particularly relevant to wind energy research, as these eddies can exert unsteady, fluctuating loads on wind turbines (Frandsen et al., 1994).

2.1.2 Vertical Distribution of Wind Energy

Wind travels over the Earth's surface and interacts with the topography and various surface elements through friction, leading to reduced velocities at low altitudes, progressively increasing with height. The logarithmic wind profile equation is a widely accepted model for estimating wind profiles within the ABL for neutral atmospheric conditions (Stull, 1988). However, it should be noted that thermal stratification may modify the wind profile in actual atmospheric conditions (Gryning et al., 2007; Businger et al., 1971; Gualtieri, 2016). The following equation relates the wind speed, $U(z)$, at a given height, z , to the friction velocity, u_* , and roughness length, z_0 (Stull, 1988):

$$U(z) = \frac{u_*}{k} * \ln \frac{z}{z_0}. \quad (8)$$

The friction velocity, u_* , is a measure of the shear stress exerted by the fluid near the surface, encapsulating the influences of surface roughness and turbulent fluctuations in the flow (Stull, 1988). Meanwhile, roughness length, z_0 , is a parameter that theoretically sets the height at which wind speed becomes null due to the surface roughness' impact on the wind profile, effectively at which height the logarithmic wind profile starts. The determination of this parameter is dependent upon the size,

shape, and distribution of surface elements that impede the air's flow near ground level. Consequently, these scalar quantities define the degree to which the surface interacts mechanically with the overhead flow. The equation also incorporates the von Kármán constant k , valued at 0.40 (Högström, 1996).

In examining the characteristics of atmospheric flow, one particularly relevant aspect emerges from the logarithmic velocity profile. This profile provides a distinctive perspective on the energy potential of wind at different altitudes. As shown in Equation 1, a cubic relationship exists between the extractable energy in the flow and its velocity. Consequently, an effective strategy to harness wind flows with more significant energy potential, is to target the upper parts of the ABL where the velocity is greater and also more stationary. This cubic relationship also highlights the importance of accurate assessment of wind speeds when considering wind energy applications, as small fluctuations in velocity significantly affect the energy potential.

2.2 Extraction of Wind Energy

Utilizing the kinetic energy in wind is nothing new, which in the modern context primarily refers to turning it into electrical energy. This process is performed by wind turbines, which use the wind to drive a generator, resulting in electrical energy (U.S. DOE, 2023). Wind turbines can be categorized into two main types based on their axis of rotation: horizontal-axis wind turbines, HAWTs, which are the most common type and resemble traditional windmills, and vertical-axis wind turbines, VAWTs, which have a main rotor shaft arranged vertically. HAWTs have become the industry standard and are typically characterized by a three-bladed rotor mounted on a horizontal axis upstream of the base tower (Hansen, 2008). The geometry of a typical HAWT is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Wind turbine schematic. Figure obtained from HowStuffWorks.

The torque applied to the generator, thus

(a) Airfoil schematic, depicting the forces acting on an airfoil moving through a fluid.

(b) Wind tunnel experiment showing how streamlines are bent around an airfoil. Picture obtained from Babinsky (2003)

Figure 3: Figures showing how airfoils are influenced by and influence the flow around them.

generating electricity, is a product of lift forces generated by the turbine blades. These forces act perpendicular to the direction of the airflow, causing the blades to rotate around the rotor hub (Manwell et al., 2010). Lift is a direct consequence of the blade's cross-sectional design, shaped like an airfoil, as depicted in Fig 3a. The lift generated by asymmetric airfoils results from their ability to bend the incoming flow's streamlines (Manwell et al., 2010), as seen in Fig 3b. A fluid particle that follows these curved streamlines experiences a centrifugal force perpendicular to the direction of motion, resulting from the change in direction. This results in the fluid particles generating a 'low-pressure' zone towards the center of the curve as the particles apply forces outward (Babinsky, 2003). Consequently, a region of low-pressure forms over the top of the airfoil. The pressure difference between the undisturbed flow and the manipulated flow results in a lift force that acts perpendicular to the wind and points towards the low-pressure region, illustrated in Fig 3a. The side with the low-pressure region is referred to as the suction surface. In contrast, the side with the relatively high-pressure region, created by the undisturbed flow path, is known as the pressure surface.

The amount of lift, L , generated by an airfoil relative to the incident wind is expressed through the airfoil's lift coefficient, C_l . Conversely, to C_l , a drag coefficient, C_d , can be derived. Drag, D , is the force exerted by a stream on an object, acting in

the opposite direction to the movement as it moves through the fluid.

$$c_l = \frac{L}{\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 c} \quad (9)$$

$$c_d = \frac{D}{\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 c}, \quad (10)$$

where c is the chord length, shown in Fig 3a.

Wind turbine designers aim to optimize the lift-to-drag ratio of the rotor blades to increase the efficiency of the energy conversion process (Manwell et al., 2010). The shape of the airfoil, the angle of attack, and the pitch of the blades are some of the factors that can be adjusted to achieve this optimal balance. Moreover, modern wind turbines are equipped with control systems that can actively adjust the pitch of the blades and the yaw of the nacelle to adapt to changing wind conditions, further enhancing the performance and efficiency of the turbine (Manwell et al., 2010).

Similarly to C_l and C_d , a power coefficient, C_p , can be defined. C_p is a measure of a wind turbine's efficiency, indicating the proportion of the wind's kinetic energy that the turbine can convert into electrical power.

$$C_p = \frac{P}{\frac{1}{2}\rho AV^3} = 4a(1-a)^2, \quad (11)$$

where a is the axial induction factor, a dimensionless parameter used to describe to which degree the wind is slowed down as it passes through the rotor plane.

$$a = \frac{U_1 - U_2}{U_1}, \quad (12)$$

where U_1 and U_2 is the wind speed just before and after the rotor-plane respectively.

The theoretical limit that dictates the maximum extractable power from the wind is known as Betz limit, or Betz' law, and was derived by Betz and Glauert in the 1930s (Manwell et al., 2010). The Betz limit establishes that a wind turbine can capture no more than 59.3%, or 16/27, of the total kinetic energy in the wind, resulting in an a equal to 0.33. Modern-day turbines are achieving power coefficients around 50% (Hansen, 2008).

The energy extraction process results in a wake behind the turbine, an area with reduced wind speeds and increased turbulence. This leads to fluctuations in both wind speed and direction, potentially impacting the power output and structural loads experienced by downstream turbines (Frandsen, 2007).

2.3 Modeling and Predicting Wake Characteristics and Behaviour

Understanding the implications of energy extraction on the airflow is an area of active research. Since these interactions alter the operational environment for neighboring and downstream turbines, the ability to accurately model them is crucial to fully utilize the wind resource. Early analytical models such as the one presented by Jensen (1983) assumed a linear relationship between the magnitude and area of the velocity deficit and the distance downstream from the rotor plane. Assuming a "top-hat distribution" of the velocity deficit, Jensen (1983) presented the following relationship; velocity for a point downstream, v_d , is linearly dependent on the scaling factor for wake expansion, a , and the distance downstream, d , given by:

$$v_d = u \left(1 - \frac{2a}{3} \left(\frac{r_0}{r_0 + ad} \right)^2 \right), \quad (13)$$

where u is the free stream velocity, and r_0 is the initial wake diameter.

Another analytical model was presented by Lissaman (1979), which since has brought forth models that, in larger part, consider the superposition of overlapping wakes (Crespo et al., 1999). Another later model presented by Frandsen (2007) models a cluster of turbines as an area of increased surface roughness to simulate and estimate the spatially averaged velocity deficit. Despite their relative simplicity, analytical models are preferred in several settings, such as wind park layout optimization, as it makes them computationally inexpensive, with Porté-Agel et al. (2020) citing their computational time in the order of seconds. Given a constricted amount of resources, this allows for modeling several iterations and scenarios.

Other, more sophisticated CFD models, based on the Reynold Averaged Navier Stokes equation, RANS, and Large Eddie Simulations, LES, have seen rapid development and adaptation in modeling turbine-flow interactions over the last decade, as computational power has become more available. An advantage of LES, contrary to

RANS, is that only turbulence with spatial scales smaller than the simulation grid scale has to be parameterized, while larger, more energetic scales can be solved explicitly (Sanderson et al., 2011). Nonetheless, the loss of information in the sub-grid scale can prove critical as turbine forces play out in this range. Some studies which have modeled turbine-flow interactions using these methods are Wu et al. (2010) and Vermeer et al. (2003).

Experimental studies have also played a crucial role in furthering our understanding of wind energy. Wind tunnel studies, like the one by Chamorro et al. (2011), provide precise control over flow parameters, such as inflow velocity and turbulence, and allow for detailed measurements. However, they do not mimic the scale and, subsequently, fully the interactions of full-sized turbines. Conversely, field experiments, such as Fuertes et al. (2018), use techniques like lidar to gather real-world data, helping validate numerical models.

The following sections give an overview of the current understanding of turbine- and farm-flow interactions and some of the concepts used to describe them.

2.4 Turbine-Defined Flow Regions

Flow structures associated with individual turbines, illustrated in Fig 4, and wind energy extraction can be classified into two categories: the near-wake and the far-wake.

2.4.1 The Near-Wake

The flow in the near-wake region, located directly downstream of a wind turbine and typically spanning two to four rotor diameters behind the rotor plane (Vermeer et al., 2003), undergoes several distinct changes as it traverses the rotor plane, and energy is extracted. The calm incident flow becomes highly turbulent due to the interaction with the turbine, as depicted in Fig 4 (top). This high degree of turbulence is a defining feature of the near-wake (Porté-Agel et al., 2020). The flow and turbulent structures within the near-wake are significantly influenced by turbine-specific factors, such as the blade profiles and the geometry of the turbine structure (Crespo et al., 1999), resulting in a complicated, three-dimensional, and varied flow distribution.

Figure 4: Schematic figure showing the flow regions resulting from the free stream interacting with a turbine. Illustrated are the instantaneous (top) and time-averaged features (bottom). Figure obtained from Porté-Agel et al. (2020)

Given its complexity, it is common to view the velocity deficit in the near wake, relative to the free flow, as uniform through the wake's center, as shown in Fig 4 (bottom). The whole of the near wake has a counter-rotating motion to the rotor's rotation due to the preservation of angular momentum (Manwell et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2011).

A notable aspect of the near-wake region is the presence of tip-vortices, which are highlighted in blue in Fig 4 (top). As wind interacts with the rotor blades, the varying pressure between the suction and pressure surfaces of the blades produce rotating air masses that shed off the rotor blades, leading to the formation of a helical vortex structure (Manwell et al., 2010; Vermeer et al., 2003; Crespo et al., 1999). Given that each blade produces such a vortex, a turbine with n blades will have a shedding frequency for the helix that is n times the rotor's rotational frequency. Furthermore, the pitch of the helix is inversely related to the tip-speed ratio. The tip vortices may hinder the entrainment of the adjacent flow by acting as a barrier between the wake and the quicker, less disturbed flow (Porté-Agel et al., 2020). As the vortices continue downstream, their vorticity gradually diminishes until they eventually dissipate (Chamorro et al., 2013; Vermeer et al., 2003).

At the same time, due to the wind's interaction with the hub and nacelle, a hub vortex develops at the center of the wake, shown in red in Fig 4 (top) (Ashton et al., 2016; Felli et al., 2011). Hub vortices represent a complex flow phenomenon characterized by a single helix rotating with the near wake (Ashton et al., 2016). The hub-vortex exhibits periodic motions, the period of which remains an area of active research (Chamorro et al., 2011; España et al., 2012). Most of the experimental studies examining hub vortices have been conducted on laboratory-sized turbines, such as those performed by Okulov et al. (2014) and Iungo et al. (2013). Consequently, there is a shortage in data regarding the behavior of hub vortices in full-scale turbines (Vermeer et al., 2003), where the nacelle-to-rotor ratio is significantly smaller. Similar to the tip vortices, the hub vortex eventually dissipates after some rotor diameters.

Since the near-wake region is highly defined by turbine-specific elements, there is a lack of comprehensive data describing the implications of basic aerodynamic rotors on the region (Vermeer et al., 2003). This deficit is often felt in both scientific and engineering environments, as it makes it harder to discern how specific design elements affect the flow behavior in this region.

2.4.2 The Far-Wake

The far-wake is the region influenced by the turbine further downstream than the near-wake. This region reaches beyond the typical spacing of wind turbines, from four to ten rotor diameters. Therefore, understanding this region's characteristics is crucial for understanding turbine-to-turbine interactions. Unlike the near-wake, the far-wake exhibits more generic traits and is less influenced by rotor-specific attributes (Crespo et al., 1999; Vermeer et al., 2003). Instead, broader wind turbine parameters like the thrust and power coefficient, which determine the velocity deficit, along with incoming flow conditions, are used to anticipate the mean flow distribution in this area (Porté-Agel et al., 2020).

In the far-wake, the velocity deficit exhibits a Gaussian distribution across the horizontal plane (Iungo et al., 2013). Characterized by a bell-shaped curve, this distribution exhibits the slowest wind speed at its center, which then progressively recovers towards the undisturbed wind speed at its edges. However, in the vertical plane, the shear generated by the incoming flow and the ground results in the velocity profile diverging from a Gaussian distribution (Chamorro et al., 2009), as shown in

Fig 4 (bottom). One significant feature of this Gaussian profile, which is inherited by the far-wake, is its self-similarity, implying a consistent velocity deficit distribution as it extends downstream. This self-similarity allows the prediction of far-wake behavior using a set of scaling laws or relationships that stay constant throughout the far-wake region (Vermeer et al., 2003). Because of its predictability, analytical models are typically favored for the far-wake (Iungo et al., 2013).

While the far-wake is less turbulent than the highly chaotic near-wake region, it still displays high turbulence relative to the free stream, with the upper part of the wake demonstrating the strongest turbulence intensity (Wu et al., 2010). This turbulence can pose risks as it may subject downstream turbines to damaging unsteady loads, thereby reducing their operational lifetime (Frandsen et al., 1994). Interestingly, the turbulence intensity near the ground appears to be mitigated by the presence of the turbine (Wu et al., 2010), resulting in a high degree of variability in turbulence intensity across the rotor in the vertical direction.

It is important to note that the far-wake is also prone to a process known as wake meandering. As shown in Figure 4 (top), this phenomenon consists of random oscillations of the entire wake relative to the time-averaged center line, typically thought to be triggered by large turbulent eddies in the incoming flow (Porté-Agel et al., 2020).

Understanding the dynamics of the far-wake is crucial for optimizing wind farm design and operation since it impacts the efficiency and lifespan of downstream turbines. Acknowledging the far-wake's self-similar behavior assists engineers in predicting the wake's influence on downstream turbines, estimating wind speed recovery (Vermeer et al., 2003), and subsequently, the optimal spacing and layout of turbines within a wind farm.

2.5 Park-Defined Flow Regions

Apart from the wake effects generated by individual turbines, the wind flow and propagation through and around a wind farm are also affected by the presence of the wind farm itself. This propagation can be broken down into different regions, with each region being defined by unique characteristics that emerge as the flow adjusts to the presence of the wind farm.

Figure 5: Schematic depicting the defining characteristics of wind farm defined flow regions

2.5.1 Wind Farm Induction Zone

The wind farm induction zone (shown in green in Fig 5) is the area upstream of the wind farm where the inflow wind speed decreases due to the presence and collective influence of the wind turbines. The characteristics of this region greatly depend on the wind farm's blockage effect, which is influenced by multiple factors such as the size of the wind farm, its layout, wind direction, and atmospheric conditions. A field study by Blegg et al. (2018) found that the average wind speed two rotor diameters upstream from the farm could be as much as 3.4% lower than the free stream.

2.5.2 Entrance and Flow Development Region

As the wind encounters the first row of turbines, energy is extracted, and turbine wakes, as described in section 2.4, are formed, introducing turbulence to the flow. The newly formed turbine wakes make the flow within the entrance region highly heterogeneous, with varying wind speeds and turbulence characteristics at different locations (Porté-Agel et al., 2020). As the wind travels downstream within the wind farm, the wakes expand and interact with each other. The flow remains heterogeneous at the turbine level in this region. However, as an internal boundary layer is formed between the turbine affected flow and the free stream, a more homogeneous flow appears above. This boundary layer continues to develop and expand as the wind progresses downstream (illustrated as the purple region in Figure 5) (Porté-Agel et al., 2020). The IBL marks the transition between the wake-influenced and undisturbed flow above.

2.5.3 The Fully Developed Wind Turbine Array Boundary Layer

The Wind Turbine Array Boundary Layer (WTABL) concept was introduced by Calaf et al. (2010) to describe the region where the entire boundary layer has adjusted to the presence of the wind farm, which occurs when the length of the windfarm is significantly large compared to the height of the ABL (shown in blue in Fig 5). This results in a spanwise- and row-averaged homogeneous flow, where the energy extracted by the turbines is balanced by momentum entrainment from the undisturbed atmosphere above, leading to what is known as an infinite wind farm scenario. In this region, there is no further loss in power production downstream due to the energy extraction of upstream turbines. A theoretical maximum limit for energy extraction, similar to the Betz limit for a single turbine, has yet to be established for infinite wind farms (Meneveau, 2019). Such a concept could help site evaluations for wind farms, as the theoretical maximum energy density of the space could be derived. The WTABL concept is crucial for understanding the complex interactions within large wind farms as it offers valuable insights for optimizing their design and operation (Stevens et al., 2017).

2.5.4 The Exit and Wind Farm Wake Region

The exit and wind farm wake region are characterized by the absence of turbine forces, which results in an acceleration in the streamwise direction due to entrainment. Momentum flux from the above flow is transported into the wake, leading to momentum recovery as the distance from the trailing edge of the wind farm increases. Both measurements and numerical models have demonstrated that the distance at which the farm wake remains non-negligible can be substantial (Wu et al., 2010), and is heavily influenced by the stability of the atmosphere (Stevens et al., 2017). Grasping the characteristics and dynamics of the exit and wind farm wake region is crucial for minimizing interactions between neighboring wind farms.

2.6 The Need For New Datasets

The vast range of scales all these intricate interactions span makes understanding them challenging. Modeling them has proven difficult, as each end of the spectrum

requires different grid resolutions and underlying assumptions. Traditionally this has been handled by focusing on the various scales separately, using assumptions and simplifications to reduce the complexity of the analysis (Veers et al., 2019). However, as the size of wind turbines and parks grows, this separation becomes increasingly untenable. The term "terra incognita," meaning "unknown land," was coined by Wyngaard (2004) to describe the scales separating the micro- and mesoscales. Terra incognita encompasses circulations spanning approximately 500 m to 1 500 m (Veers et al., 2019). The characterization of this interface is becoming increasingly crucial as turbines generate and are affected by flow features that occur within the terra incognita.

In "Big wind power: seven questions for turbulence research," Meneveau (2019) raise several questions that highlight the current lack of understanding of terra incognita. One of the questions the paper raises is whether there is a computationally inexpensive and systematic way to model the hierarchy of scales in wind turbine wakes. The models currently in use are ad-hoc, and a gold standard has yet to be established (Meneveau, 2019). A similar answer is given to how the information from large-scale circulations can be represented in the simulation of small-scale domains. Here Meneveau (2019) state that further understanding of non-equilibrium boundary layer turbulence could lead to a solution.

Calaf et al. (2010) as mentioned, define the area downstream of a wind turbine array, where the internal boundary layer created by the turbines spans the height of the ABL, as a fully developed wind turbine array boundary layer, WTABL. This is an area where circulations span a wide range of spatial and temporal scales. In the WTABL, energy entrainment from the relatively undisturbed flow above the wind park plays a crucial role (Stevens et al., 2017). However, as essential as it is, Meneveau (2019) highlight that our understanding of the phenomenon still is insufficient and that if we were to derive a maximum power density of wind parks, further knowledge of vertical energy entrainment would be essential (Meneveau, 2019). Stevens et al. (2017) also comment on the importance of understanding the WTABL, as it is necessary for designing and operating wind turbine parks, stating that the effect of the turbulent vertical flux of kinetic energy is crucial.

Comprehending the flow conditions of wind energy is paramount for optimizing energy extraction and determining the fatigue loads imposed on turbines affecting longevity. This, in turn, can significantly impact maintenance requirements and costs,

which is essential in estimating the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) for wind parks. As wind parks are investments, ensuring the accuracy of cost calculations is crucial for achieving the continued development and advancement of wind energy necessitated for NZE 2050. The current gap in our understanding of turbine wakes dynamics, and their interactions with the surrounding atmospheric flow highlight the importance of obtaining high-quality data related to these interactions that fall between explored spatial and temporal scales.

2.7 Traditional Methods for Obtaining Wind Measurements

The traditional ground-based methods of wind measurements can be broadly classified into two categories: point measurement solutions, such as meteorological towers, and remote sensing solutions, such as sodar and lidar systems. Each of these offers distinct advantages. However, both are also associated with various limitations.

Meteorological towers are well suited for long-term measurements but are limited in spatial flexibility. They measure a suit of atmospheric conditions such as wind speed and direction at different elevations, but as towers are fixed, all measurements are made at the same spatial points. This makes them an inadequate solution for in-situ measurements when attempting to capture flow phenomena in and around wind parks. Furthermore, the substantial size of these towers poses a significant challenge in terms of installation and maintenance. This, in turn, limits the potential locations for installation to easily accessible areas. Due to their high temporal resolution and accuracy, mast-mounted sonic anemometers have established themselves as the gold standard in turbulence research. However, their limited spatial flexibility hinders researchers from taking full advantage of their accuracy.

Meteorological buoys are utilized to measure wind conditions in the offshore environment. However, they are also susceptible to many of the same limitations as meteorological towers. In addition, they also so suffer from the harsh conditions associated with the metocean environment.

Ground-based remote sensing solutions, such as lidar and sodar systems, can measure complete wind profiles and, in the case of lidars, even sweeping profiles. However, these systems also have their own set of downsides. The cost of purchasing and maintaining remote sensing systems can be a significant barrier for some research

projects. Furthermore, environmental conditions can influence the accuracy of their measurements. Lidars, for instance, are dependent on line-of-sight and can be hindered by clouds, rain, and other barriers. However, the most significant limitation when discussing turbulence is their spatial resolution. Pulsed lidar systems inherently average over bins typically 25 to 50 m in length, thus making it difficult to capture turbulent fluctuations (Sathe et al., 2011).

2.8 UAARS

UAARS have emerged as a promising solution to many of the limitations of the traditional wind measurement methods mentioned (Elston et al., 2015; Bange et al., 2021). The flexibility of UAARS is perhaps their most significant advantage, as they can reach almost anywhere within the ABL, providing a wide range of spatial and temporal coverage. This makes them well-suited for capturing flow phenomena within and around wind parks and other areas of interest. Furthermore, UAARS can be easily repositioned and redeployed, providing a high degree of flexibility regarding when and where measurements are taken. The lack of a permanent ground station and supporting infrastructure is also a significant benefit. This means that the installation cost is zero, and it opens for data gathering in environments where building permanent structures is undesirable or off-limits. One environment that takes advantage of UAARS flexibility is the offshore environment, where permanent infrastructure is far more costly.

2.8.1 Some Approaches Taken to UAARS

The field of UAARS solutions has experienced significant growth in recent years due to advancements in UAV technology. Systems have become more plug-and-play, making them more accessible and user-friendly, while the associated Ground Control Station, GCS, software has also become more powerful. Additionally, the advancements in sensors and sensing technologies have enabled more accurate and precise measurements to be taken with a smaller footprint and at a lower cost. This has led to an increase in the number of different approaches and methods being used in the field of UAARS.

Fuertes et al. (2019) have developed an approach for using UAARS in measuring

turbulence and detecting tip-vortices by equipping a UAV with a fast response multi-hole pressure probe. As the pressure probe is mounted on the UAV platform, it inherently measures in a non-inertial frame of reference. To correct this, (Fuertes et al., 2019) utilized data from additional IMU sensors on the platform to transform the frame of reference to a stationary one, which can be used for further data analysis. The system’s accuracy was validated by comparing the data obtained from the UAARS to that obtained from a sonic anemometer, and it was found to be accurate (Fuertes et al., 2019).

Neumann et al.(Neumann et al., 2015) have explored an approach to estimating real-time wind speeds using the Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) measurements from a micro-UAS (mUAS). One of the key benefits of this solution is the lack of external sensors, which reduces the overall weight and cost of the system. Weight is critical in the context of UAARS, as it directly impacts flight time. Additionally, using an mUAS minimizes the inertia of the system, allowing for measuring smaller-scale wind speed fluctuations.

2.8.2 Limitations of UAARS

There are still some limitations and challenges facing the large-scale adaptation of UAARS. As of today, one of the main limitations for all rotary wing UAARS is their limited flight time, dictated primarily by the takeoff weight and battery size. The limited flight time is a significant issue as it limits the spatial coverage possible of a system. However, today’s batteries have come a long way compared to where they were years ago (Muralidharan et al., 2022), and the development of more energy-dense battery solutions continues to allow for longer flights.

UAVs weighing under 150 kg are not subject to international aviation rules but instead governed by national authorities (Bange et al., 2021), each with its own safety requirements and legal restrictions. Navigating the legislative landscape in each country can be challenging, as the regulations and permitting processes may vary widely. International interest groups and collaborations have been established to address this, such as the Joint Authorities for Rule Making on Unmanned Systems (JARUS). They aim to guide authorities and create a coherent set of regulations for UAV operations (JARUS, 2023). However, obtaining the necessary permits for missions can be a significant hurdle. The process can be both time-consuming and

convoluted, especially in countries where bureaucracy is heavily paper-based.

Over the last year, we have seen the use of drones for suspected espionage by foreign powers here in Norway (NRK, 2022). So far, we have only seen a strengthening of enforcement of current regulations. However, the Norwegian government has stated that they continuously evaluate the situation. This could potentially lead to increased regulations and stricter licensing requirements for drone pilots. As a result, operating drones could become more difficult for individuals and organizations.

2.9 SAMURAI

The SAMURAI, Sonic Anemometer on a Multi-Rotor drone for Atmospheric turbulence Investigations, system is a new UAARS being developed. SAMURAI is distinct in the integration of a full-scale state-of-the-art sonic anemometer, the Campbell cSAT3b, offering a higher degree of precision than earlier UAARS. The anemometer is to be attached to a Foxtech D130 heavy-lifting octocopter, with a Pixhawk Cube Orange flight controller operating on ArduPilot. It is currently being developed and tested by a research team led by Joachim Reuder at the Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen.

A system such as SAMURAI in the field of wind energy would allow for a greater understanding of the turbulent interactions in and behind wind farms. In addition, a fleet of such systems could generate a high-resolution dataset over the flow interactions in the wakes, helping to close the aforementioned research gap. For example, Fig 6 highlights how SAMURAI can be used to increase our understanding of turbine wake propagation, taking in-situ measurements with unprecedented resolution. Such a system would also allow for a more detailed coherence and cross-spectrum analysis of turbulent flows, as two-point measurements could easily be obtained by having several systems in the air at once.

2.9.1 The Importance of Understanding UAV-Induced Disturbances

The realization of such a system necessitates careful consideration of the Propeller Induced Flow (PIF) around the UAV that could compromise the anemometer measurements, both in the form of induced velocities and induced turbulence. In agri-

Figure 6: Illustration of how UAARS, such as SAMURAI, can be used to map the characteristics of turbine wakes. Figure courtesy of Mauro Ghirardelli

culture, UAVs have emerged as innovative solutions for pesticide application. In this context, studies have been conducted to simulate and map how the PIF of various drone configurations and ground effects can impact the distribution of pesticides. Two such studies Guo et al. (2020) and Chang et al. (2023) were reviewed to gain an understanding of PIF distribution around a drone. The insights derived from these studies aided the research team in identifying potential locations for the sonic anemometer. However, PIF characteristics are highly dependent upon the specific UAV in use. Hence, a series of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations were performed by Ghirardelli et al. (2023) for the proposed system.

2.9.2 CFD Simulations

CFD is a numerical method widely used in fluid mechanics, which uses sets of equations and computational power to solve and analyze complex fluid flow problems. These simulations employ specific mathematical models and boundary conditions to replicate physical systems as closely as possible. In the context of this project, CFD was utilized to simulate how the PIF of a UAV similarly configured to the Foxtech D130 would develop and affect its surrounding environment under different hovering conditions. Figure 7 and ?? depict the results of these simulations where a UAV weighing 15 kg hovers in 2.5 ms^{-1} wind. For further insight into the simulations performed, see Ghirardelli et al. (2023).

Figure 7: Results from the CFD simulations performed by Ghirardelli et al. (2023).

The plots show the relative velocity induced by a UAV such as the one used for SAMURAI in an environment with a background wind of 2.5 ms^{-1} . The perspective is looking down from the drone, with the wind coming from the right. The coordinate system for the simulations has been rotated to coincide with the one used in the experiments. Figures obtained from Ghirardelli et al. (2023).

Fig 7 and ?? show the relative velocity compared to the incident wind. The most prominent patterns shown in the simulations are areas of increased relative velocity above and in front of the drone and in the trailing downwash. In addition, we see an area of stagnation below the UAV, where the incident wind meets the downwash. We also identify an area of reduced relative velocities behind the drone, above the rotor plane, where the air is sucked into the rotors. The velocity of the downwash is around eight ms^{-1} at the most intense points just under the drone, with the main body showing around seven to five ms^{-1} . The area of the flow shown to be influenced by the downwash expands rather quickly below the UAV. However, the influence is less significant in the upstream direction of the incident wind. By mounting the sensor some ways out from under the drone the influence of the PIF can be substantially mitigated.

The proposed sensor mounting and the area deemed most suitable for sensor placement, based on the information gathered from the CFD simulation and the

work of Chang et al. (2023) and Guo et al. (2020), is highlighted in Fig 9. The objective is to position the sonic anemometer outside the PIF while ensuring a low center of gravity to maintain system stability. However, this decision was not based on real-world data for the relevant UAV, and all simulations should be validated. Based on this, experimental data was deemed necessary, and the formerly mentioned objectives were derived.

Figure 9: Proposed placement of sonic anemometer, and the area suspected most suitable for sensor placement (shown in red).

3 Data Acquisition

The subsequent section provides a detailed description of the experiment conducted to address the objectives outlined in Chapter 1.5. This includes a comprehensive discussion of the experimental strategy, as well as the rationale for the chosen methodology.

3.1 Experiment Design

To answer the research questions introduced in Section 1.5, a dataset mapping the PIF generated by a UAV had to be obtained experimentally while satisfying the four criteria mentioned below had to be created.

1. **Drone System Consistency:** The PIF data must be generated using a UAS representative of that used in the SAMURAI project, as the goal is to identify the optimal sensor placement within the context of this specific project.
2. **Minimal External Interference:** External influences, such as weather conditions, should be minimized to ensure that the collected data accurately reflects the UAS' PIF generation without distortion.
3. **Flow Stationarity:** The PIF structures must be given both time and space to develop and become stationary before being mapped, guaranteeing that the collected data accurately represents the system's circulation patterns under steady-state conditions.
4. **Spatial and Temporal Resolution:** The gathered data set must be of adequate resolution to discern PIF characteristics and areas suitable for sensor placement, ensuring that the analysis provides valuable insights for the SAMURAI project.

These criteria informed the methodology employed for the experiment. The requirement for drone system consistency was readily met by utilizing one of the drones employed in the SAMURAI project for the experiment. The system used was the Foxtech D130 X8, depicted in Fig 10, featuring an X8 configuration with four sets of contra-rotating rotors, each driving a 28-inch FoxTech Supreme 2880T propeller with an eight-inch pitch. Table 1 details the system's dimensions and specifications.

Figure 10: Picture of the FoxTech D130 UAV with dimensions. Picture obtained from FoxTechfpv.com

Table 1: Specifications of the FoxTech D130 x8 UAV

FoxTech D130 x8 UAV	
Specification	Value
Flight Controller	Pixhawk Cube Orange
Operating System	Ardupilot
Weight	7.5 kg 15 kg w. batteries
Dimensions	
Width	1.87 m (symmetric)
Diagonal wheelbase	1.2 m
Frame arm length	460 mm
Propulsion system	
ESC	T-Motor Flame 80A ESC
Motor	T-Motor U8 KV170
Propeller	FoxTech Supreme 2880 Pro CF Propeller

Addressing the second and third criteria posed a challenge, as they to some extent conflict with each other. To minimize interference from external forces, conducting the experiment indoors would be an effective approach. Nevertheless, this introduces spatial constraints that can impede the downwash from fully developing and becoming stationary in a manner representative of field conditions. While outdoor environments offer the necessary spatial requirements, the results would be subject to external

elements, complicating the identification of distinct characteristics. In the same way, indoor environments can give rise to secondary circulations due to the geometry and features of an enclosed space. These circulations can interact with the primary airflow, resulting in interactions that introduce noise to the collected data. Despite the challenges, an indoor experiment was deemed preferable, as the disturbances would be consistent and thus could be quantified.

When the experiment was conducted, it became apparent that none of the indoor spaces available provided adequate ceiling height to produce representative results. A lower ceiling would in turn introduce a significant amount of interference due to the ground effect generated by the UAV "hovering" at a low altitude, which would be hard to quantify. Furthermore, it was also acknowledged that mounting the drone at a sufficient height without introducing any obstructing structures posed a significant challenge. To circumvent these issues, an alternate approach of mounting the UAV at a 90-degree angle to its flying orientation was proposed, as shown in Fig 11. This arrangement allowed the downwash to develop parallel to the ground, mitigating the interference caused by the ground effect. The aforementioned approach combined with the strategic selection of a location featuring expansive bay doors that could be opened. As a result, the downwash could be directed through these doors mitigating the spatial constraint of the enclosed space, as the downwash was allowed to continue to develop outside the premises. Meanwhile, the area of interest beneath the drone stayed indoors, remaining protected from external environmental influences.

Figure 11: Schematic of how the drone was rotated in relation to its flying orientation.

Figure 12: Schematic of the installation designed to hold, power, and operate the UAV while performing measurements.

3.2 Experiment Setup

The strategy of rotating the drone necessitated a way for it to be fixed in the appropriate orientation. For this, an installation to mount and control the UAV during the experiment was designed. The resulting assembly (Fig 12) has the drone mounted to the arm of a larger structure so as not to disrupt the PIF. The base housed the Ground Control Station (GCS), a Panasonic Toughbook which controlled the drone via a USB connection and ran the "Mission Planner" GCS software, as well as two power supplies powering the drone, each delivering 23 V at a maximum current of 40 A. Power supplies were preferred as opposed to batteries as they allowed for greater flexibility when it came to run times throughout the measuring process. To position and allow for height adjustments, the assembly was mounted to a Euro-pallet, enabling the rig to be repositioned using a pallet truck. The pallet truck introduced the nearest obstruction of PIF at a distance of 2.3 m from the drone's center. Pictures of the assembly, and how the drone mounted can be seen in Fig 15b and 15c.

To ensure a meaningful comparison between the experimental results and the CFD simulations and to perform a more nuanced analysis of the PIF overall, it was crucial to satisfy the fourth criterion. To do this, five Campbell CSAT3 sonic anemometers (see Table 2 for detailed specifications) were used to measure the PIF. Sonic anemometers were chosen due to their well-established accuracy in turbulence research, high temporal resolution, and their sensitivity to small velocity fluctuations. The anemometers were mounted to a mast with a spacing of 50 cm between the

center of each measuring volume, resulting in a measuring volume centered every 50 cm from 60 cm above the ground to 270 cm above the ground. The entire array was subsequently attached to the undercarriage of an adjustable-height table, allowing for an additional 40 cm of height adjustment, with the maximum measuring height reaching 310 cm. Table 3 lists the specific measuring heights of each sonic anemometer employed during the experiment.

The coordinate system used for the experiment has the downwash developing along the y -axis in the positive direction, the x -axis parallel to the rotor plane with the positive direction being away from Wall A (depicted in Fig 13), and the z -axis is normal to the floor, increasing with height. Measurement planes, designed to intersect the downwash across the XZ -plane, were defined at intervals equivalent to the drone's rotor diameter, D , 71 cm. With the first placed at two D downstream from the rotor plane and the last at ten D . Additionally, measurement planes tangential to the downwash, spanning the YZ -plane, were defined along the centerline of the downwash and every D away from the center up to three D in positive x -direction. Each plane would span from a height of 60 cm to 310 cm. Fig 13 depicts the resulting measurement plan, where each line represents a measurement plane.

Figure 13: Schematic of how the drone was situated within the testing space, and its position in relation to the measurement planes mapped.

Table 2: Specifications of the CSAT3 Sonic Anemometer.

*: Gain and Offset Error assume temperatures within the operating window, wind speeds < 30 m/s, and wind angle between $\pm 170^\circ$.

Specification	Details
Manufacturer	Campbell Scientific
Model	CSAT3
Measurement Principle	Sonic Time-of-Flight
Path Length	10.0 cm vertical 5.8 cm horizontal
Path Angle from Horizontal	60°
Measurement Resolution	1 mm/s rms (u_x, u_y) 0.5 mm/s rms (u_z) 15 mm/s (0.025°C) rms (c) Resolution values area instantaneous measurements made on constant signal; noise is not affected by the sample rate.
Offset Error*	$< \pm 8$ cm/s (u_x, u_y) $< \pm 4$ cm/s (u_z)
Gain Error*	$< \pm 6\%$ of reading (U within $\pm 20^\circ$ of horizontal) $< \pm 3\%$ of reading (U within $\pm 10^\circ$ of horizontal) $< \pm 2\%$ of reading (U within $\pm 5^\circ$ of horizontal)
Sampling Frequency	1 to 60 Hz
Operating Temperature	-30°C to $+50^\circ\text{C}$

Table 3: Sonic anemometer and corresponding measurement heights.

Sonic anemometer	Height, h [cm]				
	H	H+10	H+20	H+30	H+40
Anemometer 5	60	70	80	90	100
Anemometer 4	110	120	130	140	150
Anemometer 3	160	170	180	190	200
Anemometer 2	210	220	230	240	250
Anemometer 1	260	270	280	290	310

To cover each plane, the array of anemometers was moved back and forth along each plane measuring the spatial structure of PIF (under the assumption of stationarity). In order to map a velocity measurement to a spatial point, distance measurements to a designated reference point were simultaneously taken using the Benewake TF02 LIDAR range finder. Two barometers were also integrated that were used to double-check the logged timestamps for each measuring height. The Campbell CR3000 data logger was used to synchronize and record data, as well as to provide power to the various components of the sensor suit. Due to bandwidth limitations with the datalogger, the sonic anemometers had a measuring frequency of ten Hz, while the LIDAR range finder and barometers were restricted to one Hz. A second Panasonic Toughbook running Loggernet was connected to the data logger, allowing real-time data access and visualization. The sensor assembly was affixed atop a stack of three euro pallets to facilitate easy relocation and the desired start height. With the aid of a jack trolley, the entire setup could be effortlessly moved, allowing it to traverse the downwash along the planes of interest effectively. The sensor assembly is depicted in Fig 14a, and 14b illustrates the interconnections between the system's components. Fig 15, shows pictures of the experiment setup. Fig 15a shows the sensor array and how it was moved. Fig 15b shows how the drone was positioned, directing the downwash out the bay door. Fig 15c depicts how the sensor array and drone were positioned in relation to each other when traversing XZ-planes.

While conducting the experiment, the center of the UAV was lifted to a height of 1.75 m, putting the higher and lower rotor sets at 2.17 m and 1.32 m, respectively. To minimize movement related to strong thrust in the arm holding the drone while the experiment was running, a diagonal beam was positioned between it and an anchoring point on the ground to add rigidity. In the interest of repeatability, the measuring rig

Figure 14: Schematic of the sensor assembly.

was lifted until the edge of the bottom pallet cleared a 3.5 cm high obstacle ensuring a consistent base height.

A stationary baseline measurement was taken to quantify the influence of background circulations in the space and to measure how long the downwash took to become stationary, the results of which can be seen in Section 5.1. For this measurement, the sensor assembly was positioned six D downstream from the rotor plane at the center line of the downwash, while the UAV was run with a 35% throttle setting. Real-time analysis of the measurements revealed a significant inflow towards the top of the open bay door. Therefore, to mitigate the intensity of the inflow and limit interference, all accessible bay doors at the location were opened during future measurements.

Another baseline test was conducted to measure the wind velocities induced by the movement of the sonic anemometers during the experiment while traversing a measurement plane. This test involved systematically moving the anemometers through the space in a controlled manner, replicating the movements experienced during measurements. By quantifying the air velocities observed as a result of the anemometer's movement, accurate assessment and correction of them could later be performed.

(a) Picture showing the sensor assembly, and how it was moved when traversing the downwash.

(b) Picture showing how the UAV was positioned within the premise.

(c) Picture showing how the UAV was mounted, and its position in relation to the sensor assembly when traversing XZ-planes.

Figure 15: Pictures from the experiment.

3.3 PIF Mapping Procedure

Mapping of PIF along all measurement planes was carried out as detailed in this section. Two throttle settings were mapped, 35% and 45%. 35% was based on the auto-hover function in Mission Planner, which determined it as the necessary throttle application for the system to hover with a takeoff weight of 15 kg, and therefore comparable with the earlier mentioned CFD simulations. The choice of 45% throttle was dictated by it being the highest attainable level before the power supplies engaged

their Over-Current Protection. Any intermediate throttle setting between 35% and 45% was considered insignificant due to the minimal variance it would present when compared to the other settings. Mission Planner was used to control the drone during the experiment, guaranteeing consistent and reliable operation throughout the testing period.

The measurement rig was moved along each measurement plane, back and forth, making six passes, ensuring a consistent and representative dataset. Upon completion of the six passes, the sensor suite was lifted by 10 cm utilizing the lifting mechanism of the table, and the process was repeated. Once data collection for all heights along one plane was complete, the measurement rig was moved to the next plane, and the process was repeated.

For measurement planes spanning the XZ-plane the adjacent wall running parallel to the downwash, depicted as "Wall A" in Figure 13, was used to provide a reliable point of reference for the lidar measurements. While for measurement planes spanning the YZ-plane a target was placed above the rotor plane (with the employed coordinate system, this implies negative y-coordinates) to serve as a reference point for the lidar. The target was chosen to be as small as possible to minimize any interference with the inflow during the experiment.

While conducting the experiment, some challenges occurred that affected the data quality and, as such, need to be considered when analyzing the data. The challenges encountered during the experiment were:

Mapping of spatial points: As the rig was moved along a plane, the rig would fail to hold a perfect orthogonal angle to the point of interest. As a result, the distance measurement would be affected. This meant that the collected data points could contain an error in the order of centimeters, and not be logged as the correct distance. To account for this, sufficiently large data sets were gathered, and as the deviation was considered random, it would be mitigated by a reasonably large dataset.

Lidar measurements: During tangential passes, the lidar system would sometimes alternate between the intended target and other spatial points within the measuring cone. This problem primarily occurred when the distance between the lidar and the target grew larger than eight meters. The result was that some of the spatial data points were not accurately mapped in relation to the intended target.

Detailed measurements of induced velocities: The experimental setup and location posed challenges for obtaining detailed measurements of the PIF across the rotor plane due to obstructing elements, such as the structure holding the drone.

Throttle application: To correctly map the correlation between throttle setting and intensity and development, the experiment would have to be run for more throttle settings. However, due to limitations of the power supplies, over-current protection would consistently be triggered for runs with throttle settings over 45%. This limitation meant that the data collected for different throttle settings were not as comprehensive as initially planned.

Spatial limitations: The experiment was conducted in an enclosed space, and as such secondary circulations were experienced. Despite the measures taken to mitigate their influence they still affected the results, most noticeably further downstream.

The main objective of this experiment was to gain insight into the development of PIF in an experimental setting, with the aim of identifying regions suitable for sensor placement. Another goal was to confirm that the velocities of PIF derived from the CFD simulations were within an acceptable margin of error. Given these objectives, most of the identified challenges experienced during the data acquisition phase could be accommodated for during the data analysis phase, albeit with some impact on accuracy. Considering the nature of the experiment, this trade-off was deemed reasonable.

4 Data Analysis

This section describes the analysis performed on the collected data, aiming to provide a representative picture of the experimental PIF generated by the UAV.

Given the confined nature of the indoor space (as discussed in Cha 3), there was a necessity to quantify the background circulations and secondary flows before commencing the primary measurements. As described, was an initial test performed to quantify these behaviors. To reduce the noise in the measurement and enhance the clarity of trends in the data, a second-order Butterworth filter with a cut-off frequency of 0.1 Hz was applied.

The data gathered from the primary experiment resulted in two datasets, Dataset 1, DS_1 , containing the three velocity components, v_x, v_y and v_z , of the flow gathered from all five sonic anemometers with a sampling frequency of 10 Hz, and Dataset 2, DS_2 , containing the distance measured, s , to the relevant reference point and barometric data with a sampling frequency of 1 Hz. The data was recorded over two days; all measurements corresponding to a throttle setting of 35% were recorded on the 24th of October 2022, while that with a 45% throttle setting was recorded on the 25th. In total, 219 760 relevant wind velocity vectors, were collected by each anemometer, and 21 976 spatial data points.

Data cleaning is an essential step to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results obtained. It involves identifying and removing or correcting errors, inconsistencies, and inaccuracies within the dataset. These issues may arise from various sources, such as data entry errors, measurement inaccuracies, or missing information. For the experimental data, the data cleaning process began with DS_2 and the correction of outlier and missing spatial values.

4.1 Cleaning and Correction of Spatial Points in DS_2

Missing values were identified using the `dataframe.isna()` function of the Pandas Python package. Instances where both neighboring data points were considered valid, and the problematic value did not align with a pattern of other faulty data points, were corrected by conducting a linear interpolation based on their neighboring values using the Pandas `dataframe.fillna()` function. This meant a data point, S_i , was

corrected following the process outlined in Eq 14. As the difference between spatial values in $DS2$ represent physical movement in the order of cm s^{-1} , linear interpolation was deemed an adequate method to negate the errors. Of the 21 976 data spatial points in $DS2$ 12 % were defined as “Not a Number” (NaN) values. After the described procedure was conducted, the amount was reduced to zero. As the correction of independent missing values resolved all missing values in $DS2$ it was concluded that the faulty measurements were random.

$$S_i = S_{i-1} + \frac{S_{i+1} - S_{i-1}}{2}. \quad (14)$$

Outliers were defined as spatial values with a delta to the previous value greater than 30 cm, $|s_i - s_{i-1}| > 30 \text{ cm}$, which would result in a movement greater than 30 cm s^{-1} , data points outside of this threshold were replaced according to Eq 14.

Another approach had to be deployed for consecutive faulty measurements, such as those witnessed when mapping YZ-planes and the lidar changed focus point. In these instances, the position profile would be displaced by a non-negligible amount for an undefined time interval, making the neighboring data points unreliable. Assuming the profile contained valid maximum and minimum distances, a linear profile was fitted over the faulty position profiles, resulting in linear interpolations such as the one shown in Fig 16. The validity of using a linear profile was based on the analysis of valid position profiles.

Figure 16: How linear profiles were fitted over faulty distance measurements

4.2 Merging *DS1* and *DS2*

In order to combine the two datasets (*DS1* and *DS2*) into a cohesive dataset for further analysis, the difference between them in temporal resolution had to be addressed. A linear temporal interpolation was applied to *DS2*, to estimate the value of nine data points at intermediate timestamps between each spatial value, resulting in an effective sampling frequency of 10 Hz. The consequent dataset, *DS2*₁₀, was then merged with *DS1* based on their timestamp to create a final dataset, *R*, containing both spatial data and a three-dimensional velocity vector for each sonic anemometer at a sampling frequency of 10 Hz.

4.3 Cleaning and Correction of Velocity Vectors in *R*

Based on the preliminary test quantifying the movement-induced wind, the component longitudinal to the direction of movement of each vector, v_d , was corrected as follows:

$$v_{d,t} = v_{d,t} - v_{corr,t} \quad (15)$$

$$v_{corr,t} = \frac{s_{t+\Delta t} - s_{t-\Delta t}}{2}, \quad (16)$$

where t indicates a specific timestamp, Δt a time interval of 10 ms, and s a spatial value.

To detect outlier velocity vectors in *R*, a representative basis for comparison had to be made. This was accomplished through creating four tensors \mathbb{XZ}_{T35} , \mathbb{YZ}_{T35} , \mathbb{XZ}_{T45} and \mathbb{YZ}_{T45} . Each tensor corresponds to a throttle setting, 35% and 45%, and the orientation of the measurement planes within it. Each matrix within a tensor represents a measurement plane, i , each row a measuring height, j , and each column, k , a 10 cm spatial interval along the measurement plane. All data points in *R* were subsequently grouped into bins covering 10 cm intervals based on their positional value, s , height value, h , and corresponding measurement plane. Each cell of the tensors was then populated with a group. The average quantity of data points within each cell over all four tensors was 35.5. The Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) method was then applied to each cell to identify outlier velocity vectors (Mauder

et al., 2013). This was accomplished by first calculating the median velocity vector, $\tilde{v}_{i,j,k}$, within each cell, and then calculating the median absolute deviation of the velocity vectors within that cell. Any velocity vector that fell outside a threshold of 2.5 MAD was considered an outlier and subsequently replaced with $\bar{v}_{i,j,k}$ of their respective cell. Any NaN vectors were also replaced with $\bar{v}_{i,j,k}$ of their respective cell using the `numpy.nan_to_num` function of the Numpy Python package.

4.4 Calculation of UAV Induced Disturbance

The mean PIF experienced by each cell was calculated as the magnitude of the mean velocity vector of that cell, using the following equation:

$$\overline{PIF}_{i,j,k} = \sqrt{\overline{U}_{i,j,k}^2 + \overline{V}_{i,j,k}^2 + \overline{W}_{i,j,k}^2}. \quad (17)$$

Another critical aspect to consider, in the context of UAARS, was induced turbulence, as regions of high variability will adversely affect the data quality collected from onboard sensors. Therefore, to further discern areas of potential sensor placement and improve our understanding of UAV-induced turbulence, the TKE for all cells was also calculated using the following equation:

$$e_{i,j,k} = \frac{TKE_{i,j,k}}{m_{i,j,k}} = \frac{1}{2}(\overline{u'_{i,j,k}{}^2} + \overline{v'_{i,j,k}{}^2} + \overline{w'_{i,j,k}{}^2}). \quad (18)$$

5 Results

In this section, the results of the data analysis are presented. The analysis resulted in 25 measurement planes: 18 spanning the XZ- and 7 spanning the YZ-plane.

5.1 Quantification of Background Flow and Movement-Induced Velocities

Figure 17a and 17b show the result of the secondary flow analysis. For these measurements, the sonic anemometer array was at base height, resulting in anemometers 1 to 5 being 260 cm, 210 cm, 160 cm, 110 cm, and 60 cm above the ground. Fig 17a shows the unfiltered data, while a second-order Butterworth low-pass filter, with a cut-off frequency of 1 Hz, has been applied in Fig 17b to reduce turbulence and highlight trends in the data that can indicate the influence of secondary circulations. Neither figure indicate the presence of any significant unwanted circulations over the recorded minute, and the downwash appears to be more or less stationary after 30 sec. However, they show that a significant inflow occurs towards the top of the array, more clearly seen in Fig 17b and the readings obtained from Sonic 1 (blue line). The inflow can be attributed to the low pressure generated within the space as the drone pushed air out of the bay door, resulting in a compensating inflow. This effect can also be seen for both throttle settings when studying Fig 31 and 33 (in the Appendix, Section B.2), where negative velocities of about one ms^{-1} are visible in the top right corner 8 rotor diameters away from the rotor plane. The mitigation strategy to reduce this counterflow effect was to open all other available doors of the hall. This resulted in a considerably weaker but still noticeable effect towards the top of the measuring planes close to the door.

(a) Time series of secondary flow measurement, taken at X: CL, Y: 6D.

(b) Secondary flow measurement with a second order Butterworth low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 1 Hz applied.

Figure 17: Time series of secondary flow measurement.

The outside temperature, when these measurements were conducted, was around 10° C. This led to an additional thermal instability between the ambient inside air and the colder inflow as it streamed through the opening, resulting in a downward motion on the right side of the opening. This triggered a rotational component in the

downwash close to the opening, as seen in Fig 37 in the Appendix Section C.2.

The analysis of the movement-induced air velocities, as described above in Section 3.2, resulted in the average induced velocities shown in Table 4, with the anemometers moving with an average speed of 0.16 ms^{-1} in (negative) x-direction.

Table 4: Average induced velocities from moving the anemometer array.

Vector	Magnitude
\overline{U}_x	0.16 ms^{-1}
\overline{U}_y	0.05 ms^{-1}
\overline{U}_z	0.04 ms^{-1}

\overline{U}_x points in the direction of movement, where a positive value indicates the flow coming toward the anemometer. \overline{U}_y is normal to the direction of movement, where a positive value indicates the flow coming from the left. \overline{U}_z is the vertical component of the flow, where a positive value represents the flow going upwards. These results indicate a one-to-one relationship between the velocity of the sonic anemometers and the induced air velocity in the direction of travel. While both the values for \overline{U}_y and \overline{U}_z fall within the range of measurement accuracy for the sonic anemometer (see Table 2). Consequently, all velocities in the direction of motion were corrected as described in Section 4.3, Equation 15 and 16.

5.2 Three Dimensional Characterisation of PIF

For measurement planes spanning the XZ-plane, the perspective of the figures is looking from the UAV along the y-axis downstream through the relevant plane, as indicated by "Perspective A" in Fig 18. Conversely, for measurement planes spanning the YZ-plane, the perspective is looking at the downwash along the x-axis from a location with a positive x-value, as indicated by "Perspective B" in Fig 18.

Figure 18: Visual representation of the two perspectives used when visualizing data.

5.2.1 PIF Across XZ-Planes

Figures 19 and 20 depict the average PIF measured across the XZ-planes. These planes are set at increments of one rotor diameter, beginning from two rotor diameters, $2D$, downstream of the rotor plane, and extending up to nine rotor diameters, $9D$, downstream.

Figure 19: Total PIF across XZ-planes at Y (35% throttle).

Figure 20: Total PIF across XZ-planes at Y (45% throttle).

The downwash of the two throttle settings, 35% (T35) and 45% (T45), are shown in Figure 19 and 20. They display similar structures and characteristics, with the primary difference being that the intensity for T45 is greater. The results also show a tendency for slightly longer rotor-defined downwash structures with an increasing throttle. Broadly speaking, the results for different distances from the rotor plane can be summarized as follows:

- **2-3D:** Four distinct hotspots are clearly visible for both throttle settings, one for each rotor set. Peak velocities within the range of six to seven ms^{-1} , and seven to eight ms^{-1} are observed at the center of the hotspots for T35 and T45, respectively. Beyond a distance equivalent to one rotor diameter from the drone's center, there is minimal observed distance.
- **4-5D:** For both the T35 and T45, the initially distinct hotspots begin to converge, forming a more consolidated and uniform downwash structure. The region with the highest velocities is centered under the drone, with peak velocities of approximately seven ms^{-1} for T45 and five to six ms^{-1} for T35. The data indicates a more pronounced onset of downwash expansion at this stage.
- **6-7D:** For both T35 and T45, the hotspots corresponding to the four rotor sets have now completely dissipated. The downwash center, marked by the region of greatest velocities, remains relatively centered under the drone's center in the T35 scenario. However, for T45, the downwash center has begun to drift to the left. Notably, the downwash primarily expands in the negative x-direction for T35, while for T45, it expands in both the negative x- and z-directions.
- **8-10D:** At this stage, the downwash center has shifted towards the left by about 0.5 D for the T35 throttle setting and around 0.75 D for T45. Moreover, for T45, there is a downward shift of approximately 0.5 D. Peak velocities around four ms^{-1} for T35 and five ms^{-1} for T45 were observed. The edges of the downwash lean more towards the bottom left for T35, whereas for T45, the expansion appears more balanced.

5.2.2 PIF Along YZ-Planes

Fig 21 and 22 show the average PIF captured along the measurement planes spanning the YZ-plane. These planes are set at increments of a rotor diameter, beginning

from the centerline, CL, of the downwash and extending outwards in the positive x-direction, up to a distance of three rotor diameters off-center.

Figure 21: Total PIF along YZ-planes at X (35% throttle).

Figure 22: Total PIF along YZ-planes at X (45% throttle).

Regrettably, the data collected for T35 at $x = 3D$ was not usable. With no substantial disturbance measured at $x = 2D$, and that T45 $x = 3D$, with T45 having been demonstrated to have a more pronounced wake expansion (see Fig 23), also shows minimal to no disturbance. Collectively these observations suggest that significant disruption along this plane is unlikely.

- **Center Line (CL):** The figures depict a distinct profile illustrating the propagation of the downwash. In the first $2.5D$ beneath the rotor plane, the plots reveal minimal downwash expansion, clearly showing the individual downwash structure of the rotor sets. The convergence of these structures is evident between three and five D downstream. The flow structure for T45 appears more defined than that of T35, and shows higher absolute velocities.
- **1D:** At a distance of one D away from the center line, the amount of PIF is substantially diminished. For T35, the disturbance emerges around $3D$ downstream and is more pronounced beneath the UAV center. In the case of T45, the disturbance is observable along the entire profile, yet it follows a similar pattern of being most prominent in the lower half of the plot.
- **2-3D:** No definitive disturbance was detected at this distance.

5.2.3 Wake Expansion

A non-dimensional measure, defined as the ratio between the downwash diameter at point Y downstream and the downwash diameter at the origin, was calculated to analyze the downwash expansion across the different throttle settings effectively. The size of the downwash was defined as the area in the horizontal direction where the y -component of the PIF exceeded one meter per second. The vertical component of the expansion was excluded as Fig 19 and 20 show potential interactions between the downwash and the ground form a distance of around four D below the rotor plane, impacting the downwash expansion in the vertical direction. The result of this comparison can be seen in Fig 23.

Figure 23: Downwash expansion as a function of distance downstream.

As supported by Fig 19 and 20, Fig 23 shows the downwash expansion to be less pronounced within the first few rotor diameters beneath the rotor plane. Up to $6D$, the expansion seems to be independent of the throttle setting. However, for greater distances, higher throttle leads to significantly wider downwash.

The vertical component of the PIF, \mathbf{U}_z , was analyzed to understand the velocities driving the expansion, and some note-worthy characteristics were shown. Fig 24 depicts the average \mathbf{U}_z captured across the YZ-planes for T45. T35 displays similar characteristics, however less prominent (these results can be found in the Appendix).

Figure 24: U_z along the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 35%)

- **Center Line (CL):** Initially, up to four rotor diameters downstream from the rotor plane, the downwash exhibits a converging trend towards its center. This characteristic signifies a phase of the downwash development where the induced velocities are concentrated towards the center. At four rotor diameters downstream, however, the downwash ceases to converge and instead begins to diverge, marking the onset of its expansion. This further corroborates the expansion profile shown in Fig 23.
- **1-3D:** These planes show a general negative U_z . However, no conclusive flow structures are depicted. Based on what was observed during the inflow measurements, and what is shown in Fig 37 ($Y = 8 - 10D$), the negative velocity could be a result of the cold inflow.

5.2.4 PIF Variability

Considering the potential impact of high variability in PIF on the quality of data gathered from systems such as SAMURAI, an analysis of TKE across the measurement planes was also conducted. TKE, as a measure of turbulence intensity, can offer insights into regions where PIF is highly variable and thus can introduce noise in sensor readings.

Observing the trends discerned from the results thus far, and that the primary area of interest for sensor placement is, as shown in Fig 9, within the first D downstream of the rotor plane. The analysis will now predominantly focus on this region, up to five D. The presented results are also limited to the more pronounced case of T45. However, for completeness and potential future reference, figures encompassing T35 and measurement planes further downstream are still included but have been relegated to the Appendix.

Figure 25: Total TKE across the XZ-plane at Y (Throttle 45%)

Figure 26: Total TKE along the YZ-plane at X (Throttle 45%)

Based on Fig 25 and 26, it appears that zones of elevated turbulence are predominantly localized within the downwash area. Notably, the regions exhibiting the highest turbulence intensity are situated at the peripheries of the downwash, where the shear interaction between the rapidly moving downwash and the relatively stagnant ambient air is at its maximum.

6 Conclusion

The research questions introduced in section 1.5, which this thesis set out to answer, were:

- **Objective 1:** Generate a comprehensive dataset of the Propeller Induced Flow, PIF, produced by the SAMURAI UAV in a calm environment, and quantify the circulation pattern in the vicinity of the UAV while hovering. This will enhance the research team's understanding of the UAS's impact on the surrounding environment during flight and its potential to disrupt the results and measurements when used as the platform for a UAARS.
- **Objective 2:** Provide realistic boundary conditions and input parameters, as well as a validation data set, for a series of CFD simulations that have been performed to simulate the influence of the UAV on the surrounding air while hovering.
- **Objective 3:** Investigate how varying the throttle setting for a hovering system alters the characteristics and intensity of the induced circulations around the drone.

6.1 Objective 1: Mapping and Characterization of PIF Generated By SAMURAI UAV

This thesis set out to generate a comprehensive dataset of the PIF generated by a UAV operating in a calm environment. This was to identify areas of little disturbance and, therefore, more suitable for sensor placement when utilizing the drone platform in a UAARS. To this end, an array of sonic anemometers was deployed to create a spatially resolved dataset of three-dimensional velocity vectors at various distances from the UAV, which can be seen in Chapter 5. It is important to note that while the geometry of the experimental space did influence the propagation of the downwash, the gathered data still provide valuable insights into the patterns and intensities of the downwash.

The analysis showed that the downwash does not significantly expand immediately downstream of the UAV, see Fig 23, but instead begins to do so after a few

rotor diameters distance. This means that, as shown in Fig 19 and 20, the area out from directly downstream of the UAV within the first few D is more or less undisturbed. Fig 24 depicts a convergence toward the wake center in this area, which then transitions into a divergence around four rotor diameters distance. However, the velocities making up the convergence are less than one m/s. We observed substantial disturbance, around four to five m/s, up to ten rotor diameters beneath the UAV, shown in Figure 19 and 20. The turbulence induced by the UAV is, in large part, contained within the downwash. The region of most significant turbulence is within the main shear zone, along the interface between the downwash and the surrounding air (as shown in Fig 25 and 26).

Considering these findings, it is clear that some areas are more suited for sensor placement than others. The experimental data collected suggest that the most suitable area for sensor placement is just beneath the UAV and at least two rotor diameters away from its center. This conclusion coincides nicely with the research team's expectations while designing the experiment, partly based on the results of CFD simulations performed by Ghirardelli et al. (2023).

6.2 Objective 2: CFD Validation

The CFD simulations, shown in Fig 7 and ??, and experimental data, Fig 19 and 21, provide a comparative analysis of downwash dynamics despite differing conditions. However, these conditions impose difficulties in directly comparing the two datasets due to the difference in background flow. The CFD simulations show a background wind of 2.5 m/s, having a noticeable impact on downwash propagation and downwash tilt. In comparison, the experimental data considers a background wind of zero $m.s^{-1}$. Between the T35 and T45 datasets, T35 is the most comparable to the system simulated and is therefore used in these comparisons.

Despite the differences in background flow, similarities are shared between the datasets. The downwash development starts with two distinct structures, as seen in Fig 21, $X = CL$, and 8a, corresponding to each set of rotors, merging around four D in the experimental data and around three D in the simulation data when compensating for the diagonal development. Analyzing Figure 8a suggest that the deflection of the upwind downwash structure, due to the incident wind, is more substantial than that experienced by the downwind structure, leading to an earlier merging in the

simulations. Peak velocities along the center line of the downwash are around six m/s in both cases, with most velocities ranging between four to five m/s.

However, differences between the datasets become more pronounced when moving away from the center line and further downstream. In the experimental data, minimal disturbance is observed for one D off the center line, and the disturbance measured emerges around three to four D under the rotor plane. Contrarily, the CFD simulations show substantial PIF at one D off the center line with greater velocities than those observed along the center line. Significant PIF is also present further away from the center line, as shown in Fig 8c. Fig 7a and 7b indicate a 'mushrooming' effect experienced by the downwash in the simulations, indicating that background flow facilitates downwash expansion perpendicular to the direction of the flow.

Given the distortion caused by the background wind in Fig 7, there is little basis for comparison with the experimental results measured across the XZ-planes, seen in Fig 19.

In conclusion, despite the disparities in background flow conditions, both datasets share similar velocities and some development characteristics. These findings give us confidence that the CFD simulations are representative of real-world scenarios, even though some caution is needed given the noted differences.

6.3 Objective 3: Correlation Between Throttle Settings and PIF

Objective 3 intended to ascertain how the intensity and structure of the downwash evolved in relation to the applied throttle. Unfortunately, due to the activation of overcurrent protection on the power supplies used in the experiment, the scope of throttle settings tested was limited to 35% and 45%.

Despite this limitation, valuable insights were derived from the available data. The structural pattern of the downwash, shown in Figure 19 to 22, remained consistent between the two throttle settings. The primary difference observed pertained to the intensity of the downwash, with T45 exhibiting a more pronounced effect than its T35 counterpart. The analysis also reveals that higher throttle application results in more substantial wake expansion. This finding is consistent with expectations,

as higher velocities within the downwash lead to a stronger shear between the wake and surrounding air, resulting in a greater momentum flux. This theory is further backed up by Figure 41 and 39, showing a higher degree of TKE along the downwash-ambient air interface for T45. However, it is important to note that our data is not comprehensive enough to establish a definitive relationship between wake intensity, wake expansion, and throttle setting.

7 Outlook

The data gathered and analyzed in this thesis did contribute to an increased understanding of the PIF generated around a UAV, more specifically the Foxtech D130, while hovering in a calm environment. However, some of the experiences made should be taken into account when performing future work.

- To map the whole downwash accurately, a bigger, more open space would be necessary to avoid flow distortion. Rotating the drone helped negate ground effects. However, the drone was not lifted high enough to achieve a symmetric downwash development, and some interactions with the ground were experienced for distances of D greater than five. The effect of the inflow also distorted the results obtained further downstream, obscuring any fine-scale structures.
- To properly understand the relationship between the strength and structure of PIF and applied throttle setting, a more extensive set of throttle settings needs to be tested. For this to be possible, another solution to powering the drone has to be designed.
- This thesis focused on the PIF generated beneath the rotor plane. In the future, it would be interesting to measure the velocities across the rotor plane and the velocities induced above the drone as well.
- In addition to the thesis work presented, has an experiment utilizing a short-range WindScanner to measure the PIF of the UAV in an outdoor environment been conducted. Comparing the dataset obtained from this experiment with the one from this thesis could further highlight how different conditions affect PIF. These effects could be explored further by designing an experiment around mounting a sonic anemometer on a high mast. Then have the drone slowly perform flight profiles on the mast. This would provide another dataset of the PIF introduced under field conditions.

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Appendices

In this section you will find additional results from the experiment that were not included in Chapter 5.

Appendix A The U_x Component of the PIF

A.1 35% Throttle Setting

Figure 27: U_x across the XZ -plane at Y (Throttle 35%)

Figure 28: U_x across the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 35%)

A.2 45% Throttle Setting

Figure 29: U_x across the XZ-plane at Y (Throttle 45%)

Figure 30: U_x across the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 45%)

Appendix B The U_y Component of the PIF

B.1 35% Throttle Setting

Figure 31: U_y across the XZ-plane at X (Throttle 35%)

Figure 32: U_y across the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 35%)

B.2 45% Throttle Setting

Figure 33: U_y across the XZ-plane at Y (Throttle 45%)

Figure 34: U_y across the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 45%)

Appendix C The U_z Component of the PIF

C.1 35% Throttle Setting

Figure 35: U_z across the XZ-plane at Y (Throttle 35%)

Figure 36: U_z across the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 35%)

C.2 45% Throttle Setting

Figure 37: U_z across the XZ-plane at Y (Throttle 45%)

Figure 38: U_z across the YZ -plane at X (Throttle 45%)

Appendix D Distribution of TKE in the PIF

D.1 35% Throttle Setting

Figure 39: TKE across the XZ-Plane at Y (Throttle 35%)

Figure 40: TKE across the YZ-Plane at X (Throttle 35%)

D.2 45% Throttle Setting

Figure 41: TKE across the XZ-Plane at Y (Throttle 45%)

Figure 42: TKE across the YZ-Plane at X (Throttle 45%)